

**ASSESSMENT OF LOW- TO HIGH-FIDELITY AERODYNAMIC MODELS FOR
PROPELLER WHIRL FLUTTER: PRELIMINARY COMPARISONS WITH EXPERIMENTAL
RESULTS**

Federico Iorio
Safran Aircraft Engines
Moissy-Cramayel, France

Valdo Pagès
Safran Aircraft Engines
Moissy-Cramayel, France

Jean-Sébastien Schotté
DAAA, ONERA, Institut
Polytechnique de Paris
Châtillon, France

Jean-Camille Chassaing
CNRS, Institut Jean Le Rond
d'Alembert, UMR 7190
Paris, France

Antoine Placzek
DAAA, ONERA, Institut
Polytechnique de Paris
Châtillon, France

ABSTRACT

Whirl flutter has become increasingly relevant in advanced propulsion systems and innovative aircraft designs. While high-fidelity aerodynamic modelling is essential for a detailed understanding of whirl flutter, low- and mid-fidelity models are still needed for early-stage design and parametric studies. This paper presents a comprehensive comparison of aerodynamic models, of increasing fidelity, for the prediction of propeller whirl flutter. Preliminary results are then compared with experimental data from the OFELIA project. Low-fidelity models are developed from recent works at ONERA, based on a unified framework that improves classical models by incorporating previously overlooked physical effects. Mid- and high-fidelity models use CFD simulations, based on potential flow and URANS methods, respectively. High variability across the models is noticed in stability boundaries prediction, but a clear trend of increasing stability margins with increasing fidelity is noticed, confirming low-fidelity ones are conservative, at least for this configuration. The high-fidelity URANS model predicts similar damping levels of experiments far from the flutter point, but none of the models accurately captures the abrupt onset of instability observed in wind tunnels tests, prompting the need for further investigation. Lastly, the influence of wing aerodynamics is analysed and found to be extremely stabilizing.

Keywords: Aeroelasticity, Whirl Flutter, 1P Loads, Propeller, Stability, Experimental, URANS, Potential Flow

1. INTRODUCTION

Whirl flutter is an aeroelastic instability affecting flexibly-mounted propulsive systems. It is generated by the interaction between unsteady aerodynamic forces on the rotor and

gyroscopic moments due to its rotation [1]. This interaction leads to a precession motion of the rotor axis that amplifies over time if the system is unstable. New unconventional aircraft engine concepts, such as the CFM RISE open fan, tend to be lighter and more flexible, increasing the risk of such instability.

Early numerical models for whirl flutter use analytical theories for the aerodynamic loads and simplified two degrees of freedom structures and rely on a weak coupling approach. The first model was published by Houbolt and Reed (H&R) in 1962 [2] and is still considered the reference model due to its simplicity: aerodynamic loads are computed from quasi-steady 2D strip theory and the rotor is only free to rotate in pitch and yaw, considering rigid blades. Recently, several improvements have been done on the classical H&R model. In 2008, Gennaretti and Greco [3] included lift unsteadiness in the calculation of aerodynamic loads using Theodorsen's and Loewy's theories adapted to rotor blades. Later, in 2023, de Gaudemaris et al. [4] developed at ONERA an advanced analytical model that accounts for all six degrees of freedom of an isolated propeller and extends the formulation to flexible blades. This new formulation eliminates some of the restraining hypotheses from the original H&R model, notably including the effect of steady loads and induced velocities. Analytical models have also been applied to more complex structures, particularly to investigate the interaction between propeller whirl modes and wing structural dynamics [5,6]. Because of their simplified aerodynamic treatment, analytical models are classified as low-fidelity models. A full review can be found in [7].

Despite these models are inexpensive and easy to implement, the assumptions under which they are derived

severely limit their applicability. For this reason, recently, researchers have focused on mid-fidelity models to simulate the aerodynamics of the propeller, such as the lifting line and the panel method [8,9,10]. Although this new approach is an improvement on analytical models, using CFD codes based on potential flow makes it difficult to evaluate the effects of certain physical phenomena, such as viscosity, compressibility and transonic regime which are crucial for the next generation of high-speed propellers. Further progress requires high-fidelity models (e.g. URANS), yet a limited number of studies to date concern the use of such models for whirl flutter. In [11], Dugeai and Verley developed and tested a method to evaluate the unsteady aerodynamic forces on a propeller based on complex deformation modes to simulate precession motion of the isolated propeller-nacelle configuration. More recently, Corle et al. [12] used a CFD/CSD strongly-coupled approach, determining the stability of a wing-propeller system through the analysis of the structure time response.

High-fidelity models are necessary for reliable whirl flutter predictions, but their computational cost is prohibitive for massive use in the early-stage design, for parametric studies and optimization, where low- or mid-fidelity models are better suited. For this reason, a wide range of aerodynamic models is explored in this paper, spanning from enhanced analytical formulations to high-fidelity CFD-URANS simulations, and results in terms of stability and aerodynamic loads are compared with experimental results. A straightforward methodology is introduced to convert results from time-domain simulations into frequency-domain aerodynamic loads, enabling the use of a simple weakly-coupled approach for stability analysis. The paper is structured as follows: section 2.1 describes the experimental setup, section 2.2 the aeroelastic coupling methodology and sections 2.3 and 2.4 give a summary of the analytical modelling framework and CFD models, respectively. In sections 3.1 and 3.2, steady and unsteady propeller loads are described. Section 3.3 presents the stability analysis results from the numerical models, while section 3.4 shows some preliminary comparisons with the experimental results. Main results and perspectives for future work are finally presented in section 4.

2. EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL METHODS

This work aims at comparing unsteady aerodynamic models, of growing fidelity, for the prediction of 1P loads and propeller whirl flutter stability boundaries. On top of the model-to-model comparison, numerical results will also be compared with experimental tests conducted at the VZLÚ (Czech Aerospace Research Centre) laboratory in the context of the European project OFELIA [13].

2.1 Experimental setup

Wind tunnel tests for whirl flutter instability detection are carried out on the W-WING aeroelastic demonstrator, which consists of a 2.56m half-span wing with a flexibly mounted 5-bladed 70cm diameter propeller powered by a 15kW electrical motor (Fig. 1). Stability conditions are assessed from the

vibrational response following turbulence excitation. The tests in thrusted conditions are performed slowly increasing wind speed until instability is reached (or until the motor was at its maximum power) at fixed propeller thrust, by modifying the rotational speed accordingly. The range of wind speeds goes from 10 m/s to 45 m/s, while the range of rotational speeds goes from 3000 rpm to 5000 rpm, so that the Reynolds and Mach numbers on the sections range approximately from 5×10^4 to 5×10^5 and from 0.05 to 0.6 respectively.

Many configurations of the W-WING demonstrator exist. Distance from propeller centre to pitch and yaw pivot points can be varied and a weight can be moved inside of the nacelle to modify propeller-nacelle assembly inertia. In this study, only the configuration with the shortest pivot lengths and the weight at the front is considered, since this combination of parameters is known to be the most unstable from numerical studies [10], and is the only one that reached instability during experiments.

FIGURE 1: W-WING DEMONSTRATOR

When a propeller operates at a steady incidence angle, it experiences in-plane forces and moments, referred to as 1P loads, that increase linearly with the incidence, for small angles. The proportionality constants are expressed as non-dimensional aerodynamic derivatives such that, as an example, the side force due to pitch angle θ is given by $F_y = q_\infty C_{y\theta} \theta$, with q_∞ equal to the free-stream dynamic pressure. In the experimental campaign, loads are determined from steady-state tests where one of the two degrees of freedom (pitch and yaw) of the propeller is constrained, and the other is varied from -20° to 20° . The aerodynamic derivatives measured are the vertical forces due to pitch (θ) and yaw (ψ) angles, respectively $C_{z\theta}$ and $C_{z\psi}$, and the pitching moments, respectively $C_{m\theta}$ and $C_{m\psi}$. These tests are performed on the W-STING demonstrator, which only consists of the propeller and the nacelle assembly. In this way, aerodynamic interactions between wing and propeller are avoided, and the missing 1P derivatives are retrieved from symmetry laws: $C_{y\theta} = C_{z\psi}$, $C_{y\psi} = -C_{z\theta}$ for the side force and $C_{n\theta} = C_{m\psi}$, $C_{n\psi} = -C_{m\theta}$ for the yawing moment. It must be noted, however, that the nacelle is not axisymmetric, so that the use of these relations results in an approximation.

2.2 Stability analysis

The proposed aerodynamic modelling follows a weak coupling approach. Unsteady aerodynamic loads due to propeller movements are obtained analytically or from CFD simulations, then applied to the Finite Element Model (FEM) of the W-WING demonstrator. The wing is modelled as a clamped beam, while pylon, nacelle and propeller are rigid bodies (Fig. 2). The propeller is connected to the nacelle by two rotational springs, allowing relative movements only in pitch and yaw. Pre-stress induced by steady-state propeller loads is neglected, as it does not alter modal frequencies or mode shapes significantly and to result in displacements of a few millimetres, even in high thrust conditions. Structural damping is also neglected, so that the equation of motion of the system is:

$$M_S \ddot{U} + G_S \dot{U} + K_S U = F_{aero}(U, \dot{U}, \ddot{U}) \quad (1)$$

Where M_S , G_S and K_S are the structural mass, gyroscopic and stiffness matrices, U represents the displacements of the degrees of freedom and F_{aero} represents the unsteady aerodynamic loads on the propeller and the wing. \dot{U} and \ddot{U} are the velocities and accelerations of the degrees of freedom, respectively. In the frequency domain, forces can be expressed in terms of a complex transfer matrix:

$$F_{aero}(\omega) = E(\omega)U \quad (2)$$

Unsteady lift on the wing is calculated from Theodorsen's theory [14], while the methodology to obtain the unsteady propeller loads are described in sections 2.3 and 2.4. This matrix includes both the aerodynamic loads due to the wing and the propeller. Using NASTRAN SOL 107 routine, the complex eigenmodes of the unloaded structure are obtained and a reduced-order model is built by considering only the modes that contain whirl motion: the 1st mode, i.e. the backward whirl (BW), and the 2nd, which is a combination of forward whirl (FW) and wing bending. The distinction between backward and forward whirl is that in the former, the direction of propeller's axis precession is opposite to its rotation, while in the latter it is the same. By projecting eq. (1) onto the modal basis thus obtained, it can be rewritten as:

$$B(\omega)\dot{q} = A(\omega)q \quad (3)$$

Where q are the modal coordinates and the matrices A and B are a combination of the structural matrices and the aerodynamic transfer matrix from eq. (2). Imposing modal displacements to take the form of $q = q_0 e^{\lambda t}$, eq. (3) can be finally rewritten in the frequency domain:

$$\lambda B(\omega)q_0 = A(\omega)q_0 \quad (4)$$

The equations of motion of the system give rise to a non-linear eigenvalue problem, which is solved iteratively via the p-k method [15]. The eigenvalue of the system is $\lambda = -\zeta + i\omega$,

where the imaginary part ω is the frequency and the real part $-\zeta$ is the modal damping with negative sign. A mode is stable if $\zeta > 0$ and it is unstable if $\zeta < 0$, i.e. in the case of negative modal damping. Points for which $\zeta = 0$ define the stability boundary.

FIGURE 2: W-WING FEM MODEL

2.3 Analytical models

The low-fidelity aerodynamic modelling framework, recently developed at ONERA by de Gaudemaris et al. [4], is based on an analytical formulation following the ideas of the original H&R model. Aerodynamic loads (lift and drag) are calculated independently on 20 blade sections, then integrated radially and summed over all blades to obtain the total propeller loads. Since a linearized approach is used, forces and moments are expressed as a linear combination of the propeller displacements (and their time derivatives) and some non-dimensional coefficients. As an example, the side force and yawing moment are given by:

$$F_y = q_\infty S \left(C_{y\theta} \theta + C_{y\psi} \psi + C_{yq} \frac{R}{V_\infty} \dot{\theta} + C_{yr} \frac{R}{V_\infty} \dot{\psi} + C_{yv} \frac{1}{V_\infty} \dot{y} + C_{yw} \frac{1}{V_\infty} \dot{z} \right) \quad (5)$$

$$M_z = q_\infty S D \left(C_{n\theta} \theta + C_{n\psi} \psi + C_{nq} \frac{R}{V_\infty} \dot{\theta} + C_{nr} \frac{R}{V_\infty} \dot{\psi} + C_{nv} \frac{1}{V_\infty} \dot{y} + C_{nw} \frac{1}{V_\infty} \dot{z} \right) \quad (6)$$

Where S is the swept area of the propeller and D its diameter. Similar expressions are used for the vertical force F_z and the pitching moment M_y . Axial force and torque are not considered because they only add second order effects. Given the linearity of loads with respect to displacements, eq. (5), (6) and their equivalent ones for other load components can be rewritten in matrix form. All coefficients multiplying displacements are grouped into the aerodynamic stiffness matrix K_A while the coefficients multiplying velocities are grouped into the aerodynamic damping matrix C_A . If non-circulatory lift terms are considered, loads are also dependent on accelerations, and the coefficients that multiply them are grouped into the aerodynamic mass matrix M_A . Eq. (5), (6) and their counterparts are therefore rewritten in matrix form as:

$$F_{aero} = -M_A \dot{U}_p - C_A \dot{U}_p - K_A U_p \quad (7)$$

With $U_p = \{y, z, \theta, \psi\}^T$ representing propeller centre displacements and rotations. The complex transfer matrix, as defined in eq. (2), is then obtained in the frequency domain as:

$$E(\omega) = \omega^2 M_A - i\omega C_A(\omega) - K_A(\omega) \quad (8)$$

Each one of the non-dimensional coefficients in eq. (5), (6), and their counterparts can be calculated as a blade integral, akin to the original H&R formulation:

$$C_{ij} = \phi_{1,ij}(\Omega, V_\infty, \rho_\infty) \int_{R_i}^{R_e} \phi_{2,ij}(c, \bar{W}, c_l, a_l, \omega) dr \quad (9)$$

The functions $\phi_{1,ij}$ include the dependency of the coefficients on the operating point of the propeller (rotational speed, free-stream velocity and air density) and its macroscopic geometry (number of blades and swept area). The functions $\phi_{2,ij}$ include instead the dependency on local flow quantities and blade geometry: chord c , relative velocity \bar{W} , lift coefficient c_l and its derivative $a_l = \partial c_l / \partial \alpha$ with respect to the sectional angle of attack α , motion frequency ω . These functions must be integrated along the radius from blade root R_i to blade tip R_e . As an improvement of the H&R model, the influence of the steady airflow on the aerodynamic coefficients is not neglected, allowing application to thrusting propellers. The correct incident wind speed on every blade section is calculated through the BEMT (Blade Element Momentum Theory) algorithm [16]. The unsteady lift force on a blade section is calculated analytically using the generic formula:

$$l' = q_{rel} \Re \left\{ \mathcal{F}_x(\omega) \frac{u'_x}{\bar{W}} + \mathcal{F}_t(\omega) \frac{u'_t}{\bar{W}} + \mathcal{F}_\epsilon(\omega) \frac{c\epsilon}{\bar{W}} \right\} \quad (10)$$

Where q_{rel} is the relative dynamic pressure, u'_x , u'_t and ϵ are the axial velocity perturbation, tangential velocity perturbation and pitch rate of the blade section, and finally \mathcal{F}_x , \mathcal{F}_t and \mathcal{F}_ϵ are complex-valued lift-lag functions for the relative perturbation quantities. Velocity perturbations are directly related to the structural degrees of freedom, so that these functions model the amplitude and the phase lag of the unsteady lift caused by propeller motion. Eq. (10) establishes the frequency dependency of aerodynamic coefficients, since a combination of lift-lag functions appear in $\phi_{2,ij}$, under the integral. Any analytical model for unsteady lift, provided it is linear with respect to velocity perturbations, can be used within this framework. In this study, three models are used and compared:

- Greenberg's model [17]: used to calculate unsteady lift due to pitching and plunging motion of an aerofoil in a flow with harmonic chordwise speed variations.
- Loewy's model [18]: adaptation of Greenberg's

model to a rotary wing. This model accounts for the wake's influence on the aerofoil aerodynamics.

- Sears' and Horlock's model [19]: calculates unsteady lift of a stationary aerofoil in a flow with harmonic oscillations of chord-wise and transverse speeds.

The model has been further extended to take into account the sectional drag and pitching moment coefficients. Moreover, the lift curve is linearized around the steady-state angle of attack at each blade section. These modifications aim at improving the predictions of the model in cases where parts of the blade begin to stall, so that lift is no longer linear and drag becomes important. Non-linear aerofoil coefficients are obtained, for angles of attack from -20° to 25° and for 7 Reynolds numbers in the estimated experimental range on 20 blade sections, using the code XFOIL [20]. Compressibility effects and tip-losses are accounted for through Kaplan [21] and Prandtl [22] correction factors, respectively.

2.4 CFD models

Mid- and high-fidelity models use Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) to calculate the aerodynamic forces on the propeller. While low-fidelity models, as described in the previous paragraph, use explicit equations to calculate rotor loads, higher fidelity models require the solution of a system of differential equations. Transfer functions are obtained from a particular post-processing of results obtained from time simulations.

FIGURE 3: VISUALIZATION OF TIP-VORTICES FROM A DUST – ULLM SIMULATION USING THE Q-CRITERION

Mid-fidelity models from DUST [23], an open-source code based on 3D unsteady potential flow theory and vortex particles method (VPM), are used. The geometry of the propeller can be defined in three different ways, which defines the model in use:

- Unsteady Panel Method (UPM): blades are discretised into quadrilateral flat panels both on the pressure and on the suction sides. This model allows for the representation of thickness effects, which may be relevant in the blade root sections.
- Unsteady Vortex Lattice Method (UVLM): blades are modelled as a zero-thickness 2D vortex sheets. For each blade, the panels composing the vortex sheet are placed on the camber line of each section.
- Unsteady Lifting Line Method (ULLM): blades are discretised radially in a finite number of points on which aerofoil-equivalent aerodynamic loads are

applied, resulting in a 1D lifting line. No chordwise discretization is needed for this model, making it suitable for slender lifting bodies, such as propeller blades.

Mixed modelling can be used in DUST, to simulate the aerodynamic interactions between the propeller and other bodies. As an example, Fig. 3 shows a simulation in which propeller blades are modelled with ULLM (chord lengths added for visualization) and the spinner with UPM. The spinner is not present in other simulations because of its negligible influence on stability.

All methods rely on free wake modelling, so that at each time step of the simulation, vortex particles are released from the blades trailing edges to enforce Kutta condition and advected at local flow velocity. In UPM and UVLM, loads are computed from the intensities of doublets and sources on each panel of the blades, which are in turn determined at every time step by enforcing the non-penetration condition on the surface, and the intensity of the vortex particles in the wake. Compressibility dependency is recovered by applying the Prandtl-Glauert correction factor. In ULLM, steady loads are calculated from tabulated lift, drag and pitching moment coefficients, which already include dependency on angle of attack, Mach and Reynolds numbers, using an iterative algorithm. Unsteady loads are instead calculated from an unsteady version of the Kutta-Joukowski theorem. ULLM uses the same XFOIL-derived coefficients as the analytical models.

In all models, blades are discretised radially into 21 segments, using the known section geometries at 20 points from root to tip. 12 panels in the chord direction are used for both UVLM and UPM and the time step is chosen to correspond to an azimuthal step of 8° , based on a convergence study on steady loads.

FIGURE 4: PROPELLER MESH FOR URANS SIMULATIONS

The Unsteady Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes (URANS) model from the Safran-ONERA CFD code elsA [24] is used as the high-fidelity reference. In this model, the Navier-Stokes equations are solved in every point of the 3D simulation domain, with turbulent fluctuations represented through Reynolds averaging rather than direct solution. In particular, the Menter $k-\omega$ SST turbulence model [25] is used. Rigid body motion of the propeller is introduced in the simulations by additional grid

velocities (through the ALE formulation). Unlike mid-fidelity models, high-fidelity ones require a volume mesh, drastically increasing computational cost. In this study, a 360° mesh of 15 million cells for the full propeller is used (Fig. 4), replacing the nacelle by an axisymmetric spinner prolonged axially to the end of the domain. The simulation domain is a cylinder that extends from $5D$ upstream to $5D$ downstream and has diameter of $10D$. Time step corresponds to an azimuthal step of 1° .

Frequency-domain transfer functions are identified from forced response to pulsed perturbations of each degree of freedom, as in [26]. To summarize the method, it can be divided into the following steps:

1. Simulation of the steady-state, until convergence is reached. Six or three rotor revolutions are required in mid- and high-fidelity models, respectively.
2. One of the propeller's degrees of freedom is perturbed by means of an imposed pulsed motion (see Fig. 5).
3. The transfer function between the displacement X_j and the load component F_i is then calculated from their Fourier transforms as:

$$E_{ij}(\omega) = \frac{\text{FFT}\{F_{i,pulse}(t) - F_{i,steady}\}}{\text{FFT}\{X_{j,pulse}(t) - X_{j,steady}\}} \quad (11)$$

Steps 2 and 3 are repeated for every degree of freedom j . For the propeller-only cases, given that the steady flow is axisymmetric, only one simulation with pitch rotation and one with vertical translation are carried out. When the wing is included, symmetry relations are no longer valid and four simulations are needed to construct the full propeller transfer matrix.

FIGURE 5: PULSE FUNCTIONS FOR PITCH ANGLE IN MID- AND HIGH-FIDELITY SIMULATIONS

In mid-fidelity simulations, pulse duration is set to two rotor revolutions, while in high-fidelity simulations it is set to three revolutions to provide smoother motion to avoid triggering potential non-linearities. For the same reason, the pulse widths are set to 2° and 1.5cm for mid-fidelity and 0.25° and 0.1cm for high-fidelity. Moreover, a triangular pulse shape is used in mid-fidelity while a sinusoidal shape is used for high-fidelity. All these differences are made clear in Fig. 5, where mid- and high-fidelity pulse functions for pitch angle are compared. The pulse method is validated by means of harmonic simulations at given frequencies for the elsA – URANS and the DUST – ULLM

models. The advantage of the pulse method is that only one simulation per degree of freedom is needed to recover the transfer function in all the frequency range of interest. This advantage is even more evident in this study because whirl flutter frequencies are very low with respect to rotation frequency, which would require extremely long harmonic simulations.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

FIGURE 6: STATIC PROPELLER THRUST FOR 5° AND 10° BLADE PITCH ANGLES

Prior to analysing 1P loads and whirl flutter, the models are validated with respect to static propeller thrust. In Fig. 6, results are shown at 3600 rpm and for two blade pitch $\beta_{75\%}$ settings. All models are found to be in good agreement with experimental results. The BEMT (analytical) and ULLM models exhibit accuracy comparable to that of URANS, while other mid-fidelity models tend to overpredict thrust. It is observed that models tend to diverge from experimental data at higher speeds, due to large negative angles in the blade tip region.

3.1 1P loads

FIGURE 7: 1P LOADS: REFERENCE FRAME AND RESULTS AT $\Omega = 3600$ RPM, $V_\infty = 10$ M/S AND $\beta_{75\%} = 10^\circ$

1P loads are experienced by rotors in static incidence, as a result of the periodic variation of angles of attack and relative wind velocities on each blade [27]; summation over all blades gives constant in-plane loads in the propeller reference frame, linear with respect to incidence angle (for small angles). As an example, 1P forces derivatives are shown in Fig. 7 for the case $V_\infty = 10$ m/s, $\Omega = 3600$ rpm and blade pitch $\beta_{75\%} = 10^\circ$ (Greenberg’s model is used to represent low-fidelity and ULLM mid-fidelity). From a mechanical point of view, varying the angles of attack over one rotor revolution causes the azimuthal lift distribution to become asymmetric. This results in a net upward force and a yawing moment. Considering the unsteadiness of the flow, through the effects of shed vorticity, results in the appearance of a side force and a pitching moment. Although these load components are less intense, the side force in particular is crucial to whirl flutter.

Fig. 8 shows the comparison of aerodynamic derivatives measured experimentally with those obtained from numerical models for different wind speeds at the rotation speed of 3600 rpm and 10° blade pitch. Once again, the low- and mid-fidelity models are represented by Greenberg and ULLM respectively,

FIGURE 8: COMPARISON OF 1P LOADS COEFFICIENTS AT $\Omega = 3600$ RPM AND $\beta_{75\%} = 10^\circ$

for simplicity. The coefficients are expressed in the propeller reference frame, and the lag angle is defined as the angle between the vertical axis and the force/moment resultant. In general, the amplitude of force and moment is predicted more accurately and with less dispersion across models than the lag angle. This is because $\delta_{F\theta}$ and $\delta_{M\theta}$ are strongly dependent on the horizontal $C_{y\theta}$ and pitching $C_{m\theta}$ components, while the amplitude is mostly given by the vertical $C_{z\theta}$ and yawing $C_{n\theta}$ components. As mentioned previously indeed, these components originate from the unsteadiness of the flow and are usually of lower intensity. Despite the bigger discrepancies in lag angles, general trends are still reproduced by the models. The moment lag $\delta_{M\theta}$ increases with wind speed except for the lifting line model, which predicts a linear decrease, and URANS at low speed. The experimental force lag $\delta_{F\theta}$ increases much faster than predicted by the models. In particular, it reaches 120° at 30 m/s, meaning that the resultant force is in the south-west quadrant, whereas all models predict it to be in the north-west.

At low wind speed, the accuracy of low- and mid-fidelity models is expected to diminish. This degradation occurs because, in the low advance ratio regime, the rotor wake unsteadiness becomes more relevant. Analytical models generally neglect the presence of the rotating wake, except through simplified theories (such as Loewy's model), whereas mid-fidelity models natively incorporate it but are limited by the assumptions of potential flow. The same observations regarding IP loads can be done for other configurations tested experimentally, with different rotational speed and blade pitch.

3.2 Transfer functions

Previous research, including the work by Koch et al. [10], showed that the coefficients $C_{y\theta}$ and $C_{n\theta}$ have the strongest influence on stability. Specifically, increasing the side force coefficient $C_{y\theta}$ tends to stabilize the system, and decreasing the yawing moment coefficient $C_{n\theta}$ has an even stronger stabilizing effect. In Fig. 9 models are compared in terms of aerodynamic

coefficients, and the URANS is shown to predict at the same time the highest $C_{y\theta}$ and the lowest $C_{n\theta}$, so that it is expected to yield the most stable behaviour compared to the others. These two coefficients are obtained as the non-dimensional real parts of the $E_{y\theta}$ and $E_{\psi\theta}$ components of the transfer matrix, representing aerodynamic added stiffness. On the other hand, the coefficients C_{yq} and C_{nq} are obtained as the non-dimensional imaginary parts of $E_{y\theta}$ and $E_{\psi\theta}$ divided by the frequency, representing aerodynamic added damping. ULLM uses tabulated aerofoil data, improving the accuracy of steady loads calculation but limiting that of unsteady loads. In contrast, UPM does not use precomputed steady loads, but employs a 3D mesh for propeller blades, capturing thickness effects. Because of these complementary approaches, ULLM best matches URANS results for some coefficients, while UPM does so for the others, making them the closest to URANS overall, while UVLM is positioned between them. Loewy's model is the analytical one that best replicates higher fidelity trends, in contrast to Sears-Horlock's and Greenberg's, which show inverse trends for $C_{y\theta}$.

In Fig. 10, the same coefficients are shown as a function of wind speed, at constant 50N thrust, at the identified backward whirl frequency (from 12.9 rad/s to 9.73 rad/s). For reference, at 30 m/s, $\Omega = 4006$ rpm: the same observations of Fig. 9 can be made but the difference between URANS and other models for $C_{y\theta}$ is amplified. Relative positions of the models do not change drastically with wind speed, hinting that their comparative behaviour in terms of stability remains unchanged.

3.3 Stability diagrams

Typically, the BW mode is the one that becomes unstable. An example of frequency and damping evolution of the modes for fixed wind speed and varying rotational speed is presented in Fig. 11, using the ULLM model. The BW mode is characterized by diminishing frequency and lower damping, which can lead to a zone of instability. On the other hand, the FW mode is always stable and shows growing frequency and damping values.

FIGURE 9: AERODYNAMIC COEFFICIENTS AT $\Omega = 3600$ RPM AND $V_\infty = 30$ M/S

FIGURE 10: AERODYNAMIC COEFFICIENTS AT FIXED 50N THRUST AT THE BW MODE FREQUENCY

Frequency and damping of the BW mode do not show significant variation between the W-WING and the W-STING model, meaning that the structural effect of the wing is not as important as its aerodynamics, which is instead found to be stabilizing on both modes, especially the FW. It is anyway found that adding the wing to the mechanical model increases, very slightly, stability margins, as already reported in other studies [9,28] although not visible in the figure because curves overlap.

while values above the boundary provide sufficient stiffness for stability. For reference, experimental W-WING stiffnesses are $K_\theta = 797.15$ N.m/rad and $K_\psi = 956.0$ N.m/rad, meaning that all the models predict the system to be stable, as confirmed in wind tunnel tests.

A clear pattern is shown: the system becomes more stable as the modelling fidelity grows, from analytical models to UVLM and ULLM, UPM and finally URANS. This is coherent with the coefficients shown in Fig. 9: as it is the BW mode to become unstable, a greater side force F_y opposes the whirl motion, while a greater yawing moment M_z favours it. Given that variations in mounting stiffnesses also cause variations in modal frequency, curves from different models show qualitatively distinct behaviours. These differences originate indeed from the different evolutions of some aerodynamic coefficients with frequency, as shown in Fig. 9.

FIGURE 11: FREQUENCY AND DAMPING EVOLUTION OF BW AND FW MODES AT $V_\infty = 35$ M/S

The stability of the system is usually studied as a function of the pitch and yaw mounting stiffnesses, respectively K_θ and K_ψ , for a given operating point. In Fig. 12, the stability boundaries at $\Omega = 3600$ rpm and $V_\infty = 30$ m/s are shown: configurations with K_θ - K_ψ values in the lower left area under the curves are unstable,

FIGURE 12: STABILITY BOUNDARIES FOR $\Omega = 3600$ RPM AND $V_\infty = 30$ M/S, COMPARISON OF MODELS

As demonstrated in [10], however, the ranking of the models in terms of stability can change according to structural parameters, such as pitch and yaw pivot length, or to the operating conditions of the propeller.

In Fig. 13, the same stability boundaries of Fig. 12 are shown, but only the DUST – ULLM and the elsA – URANS models are considered, to show the comparison with results obtain when neglecting aerodynamic forces on the wing. As anticipated from Fig. 11, wing aerodynamics has a strong stabilizing effect on mid-fidelity models, while URANS model is almost insensitive.

FIGURE 13: STABILITY BOUNDARIES FOR $\Omega = 3600$ RPM AND $V_\infty = 30$ M/S, EFFECT OF WING AERODYNAMICS

In Fig. 14, stability diagrams at the experimental stiffnesses K_θ and K_ψ in terms of wind speed V_∞ and rotational speed Ω , in the operational range of wind tunnel tests, are plotted. The comparison between the models without wing aerodynamics is shown, whereas Fig. 15 presents the same comparison including it. In these diagrams, the instability region is located in the top-right corner, at higher speeds. Due to the high computational cost of tracing these curves, only low- and mid-fidelity models until the UVLM are used. An unusual shape of the curves, with respect to that obtained with the original H&R model is revealed: two critical wind speeds exist for a given rotational speed (conversely, two critical rotational speeds exist for a given wind speed), as already seen in damping curves from Fig. 11. The physical nature of this phenomenon lies in the inclusion of steady propeller loads and aerodynamic drag in the analysis. Increasing rotational speed at fixed wind speed causes an increase in propeller thrust and torque, which is known to be stabilizing [8,10], hence giving a positive slope in the horizontal branch of the curves. The slope of the vertical branch is instead caused by the combination of negative propeller thrust and drag: notice how UVLM, which does not account for aerofoil drag, produces curves that extend farther to the left.

FIGURE 14: PREDICTED STABILITY BOUNDARIES WITHOUT WING AERODYNAMICS

FIGURE 15: PREDICTED STABILITY BOUNDARIES INCLUDING WING AERODYNAMICS

Notably, since the curves are obtained with the same blade pitch angle in all the points, close to the bottom-right corner of the plot the blade root operates in stalled conditions, while in the top-left corner the blade tips experience large negative angles. In these conditions, lift coefficient is no longer linear and drag coefficient increases sharply; for this reason, the accuracy of all low- and mid-fidelity models is expected to drop in these regions. The effect of wing aerodynamics is to stabilize the system, as is clearly seen by comparing Fig. 15 and Fig. 14. Anyway, the influence is different depending on the model: as an example, while Loewy’s model is closer to Greenberg’s without the wing, it becomes closer to Sears-Horlock’s when the wing is included. Remarkably, despite results are widely dispersed

FIGURE 16: BW (TOP) AND FW (BOTTOM) MODE FREQUENCY AND DAMPING AT FIXED 50N THRUST

FIGURE 17: BW (TOP) AND FW (BOTTOM) MODE FREQUENCY AND DAMPING AT FIXED 100N THRUST

across models, at high V_∞ and Ω values, the slopes ($dV_\infty/d\Omega$) of the stability boundaries are equal.

3.4 Modal frequency and damping prediction

Modal damping and frequency for the 50N and the 100N cases are shown in Fig. 16 and Fig. 17 respectively, for both BW and FW modes. The evolution of rotational speed Ω needed to keep constant thrust is traced in Fig. 18 for all experimental cases; the critical points for each model could therefore be identified by superposition of these curves on Fig. 15. For each model, blade pitch is adjusted to match the desired thrust level at $V_\infty = 30$ m/s for the 100N case and at $V_\infty = 35$ m/s for the 50N case. Consequently, small thrust differences arise at different wind speeds. However, a sensitivity analysis demonstrated that such variations have a negligible impact on frequency and damping, since the mechanical effect of changing

the rotational speed is more important than the aerodynamic effect of changing blade pitch, other factors being equal.

Globally, the same trends of the K_θ - K_ψ (Fig. 12) diagrams are revealed: the stability margins increase with the fidelity of the aerodynamic modelling, and it is observed that URANS results are significantly different from those of other models. At $T = 50$ N (Fig. 16) no instability is found experimentally, which is confirmed numerically by URANS, although other models predict a critical point at different wind speeds, scattered from 31.2 to 42.5 m/s. While all other models predict a monotonically decreasing modal damping, URANS predicts it to be increasing. However, the growth slows down with increasing wind speed, hinting that the same trend of the other models is recovered at even higher values. At $T = 100$ N (Fig. 17), Loewy's and Sears-Horlock's models cross the zero-damping line at 32.9 and

34.9 m/s respectively, while the experimental critical point lays somewhere in between 34 and 35 m/s. Despite this coincidence, overall accuracy with respect to damping levels remains limited, especially near the flutter point where the slopes of the numerical curves deviate significantly from the experimental one. The same trend of increasing BW damping is found with the URANS model and, once again, the growth slows down at higher wind speeds. In general, regarding BW mode damping, it can be said that the URANS model provides better results far from the flutter point, followed by UPM and ULLM, then UVLM and low-fidelity models. It is also noticed that results converge at lower speed. What is missing, in every model, is the fast decay of the BW mode damping at the onset of instability. Regarding frequency, numerical results are more consistent but, in both cases, a different slope is observed when compared to experimental data.

Concerning the FW mode, all models are consistent both in frequency and damping. Experimental data is degraded at high wind speeds but it seems to confirm numerical trends, especially at $T = 50\text{N}$.

FIGURE 18: ROTATIONAL SPEED NEEDED FOR CONSTANT EXPERIMENTAL THRUST LEVELS

Finally, the effect of propeller thrust on stability is analysed (Fig. 19). Experimental data indicate that instability is reached sooner with higher thrust, but all the models show little to no difference. Considering the shape of the stability boundary that emerged from Fig. 15, this result might be explained by a shift to the right of the experimental boundaries, with respect to the numerical ones. The behaviour of numerical models might be explained as a compensation of two phenomena: on one hand, increasing the rotational speed is destabilizing from a purely mechanical point of view, but on the other hand thrust is stabilizing. Experimental results might therefore reveal that the mechanical effect of rotational speed prevails.

4. CONCLUSION

In this study, a systematic comparison of aerodynamic models for propeller whirl flutter is provided, and numerical predictions are benchmarked against preliminary experimental data from the OFELIA project test campaign. Despite all models have been validated with respect to static propeller loads, discrepancies remain in the prediction of IP loads. Side force and yawing moment have the greatest variability across models,

FIGURE 19: INFLUENCE OF PROPELLER THRUST

although they are crucially the most relevant loads for whirl flutter stability.

The pulse method is implemented to obtain transfer functions in the frequency domain from CFD simulations. The following trends are revealed:

- Stability margins increase with the modelling fidelity, going from analytical to URANS, with the mid-fidelity models positioned in the middle. UPM or ULLM best matches URANS, depending on the operating point of the propeller.
- Different models show different dependency on frequency, meaning their comparative behaviour changes with the structural stiffnesses, as highlighted by the K_θ - K_ψ stability curves. When evaluated at the BW frequency at fixed thrust, the evolution of the coefficients with wind speed is consistent, implying that their comparative behaviour for a given configuration is not supposed to change. As for stability prediction, either UPM or ULLM gives the best results compared to URANS. Loewy's model stands out as the best analytical one.
- Wing aerodynamic loads play an important role on the stabilization of the BW mode. It is yet to understand why it affects each propeller model differently: it is seen that its impact on stability is minimal with URANS but it's pronounced with ULLM.
- Instability in wind tunnel tests is more abrupt than predicted numerically. While all models show a steady damping decay towards the zero, a sudden transition to negative values is seen in experiments. Before flutter, anyway, URANS give the best results.

A particular shape of Ω - V_∞ stability boundaries is revealed by numerical results, qualitatively different from the curves obtained with the original H&R model: notably, two critical wind speeds exist for the same rotational speed, and vice versa. This difference is due to the inclusion of static propeller loads and drag. The improved analytical models developed for this study are able to correctly predict the shape of the boundaries.

Further investigation is needed to bridge the gap between numerical and experimental results. The primary goal is to understand the instability mechanism that was revealed in wind tunnel tests: none of the aerodynamic models is capable of predicting it, so that focus should also be put on the structural model and the coupling strategy. To better understand the differences between the models, unsteady aerodynamic loads and flow field (for CFD models) should be analysed locally, to gain insight into the underlying physical phenomena responsible for their different behaviours. The present analysis was instead limited to integrated rotor loads. Finally, given the system's high sensitivity to wing aerodynamics, its modelling can be refined through the use of higher fidelity models, capturing the effects of propeller-wing mutual interaction.

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